

WORK TOLERANCE OF MATHEMATICS TEACHERS IN RELATION TO TEACHING PERFORMANCE: BASIS FOR INTERVENTION

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Work Tolerance of Mathematics Teachers in Relation to Teaching Performance: Basis for Intervention

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Abstract

This study determined the relationship between work tolerance and Teaching performance of the Mathematics teachers of the District of Isabela 1 for School Year 2023-2024. A researcher-made questionnaire was administered to 96 samples as respondents of the study. Frequency and percent distribution, Mean, Mann-Whitney U-Test and Kruskal-Wallis H-Test, and Goodman-Kruskal's Gamma (G) or Gamma Coefficient were the statistical tools used in the study. The results revealed that the level of work tolerance of mathematics teachers in terms of physical demands is high and very high in terms of psychological demands. The results also revealed that the teaching performance of the mathematics teachers, based on their IPCRF rating, is outstanding. In terms of differences, there is no significant difference between the level of work tolerance of mathematics teachers and sex, age, socio-economic status, and number of years in teaching. A significant difference is found between the level of work tolerance of mathematics teachers and highest educational attainment. In terms of relationship, the level of work tolerance of mathematics teachers does not significantly affect their teaching performance.

Keywords: *work, tolerance, teachers, mathematics*

Introduction

Teaching, as what has been considered by many, is a noble work. As a lifestyle, it provides many perks, including the flexibility to work close to the place where one lives, guaranteed paid holidays and vacation leave, and permanent employment status in public institutions. In schools, teachers are one of the most significant persons (Batuiigas, 2022).

Khan (2019) posited that an organization's productivity may be enhanced and made more productive through the quality of work and employee attitude. In a school setting, the educational process encompasses more than just the curriculum; instructors' effectiveness as instructional facilitators has an impact on the overall quality of education. One of the key elements influencing students' conduct and academic success is the caliber of teachers' work and their commitment to their field. According to Sharma and Dhar (2018), for educators to make a substantial impact on the development of the school and its students, they must be passionate about what they do.

On the other hand, work tolerance of teachers play a vital role on how they are facing reality in the field of their professional discipline. Work tolerance refers to the ability or endurance to teach effectively and efficiently despite varying degrees of psychological, physical, or both stresses. It is viewed as an essential aspect of a teacher's whole being, which might affect a teacher's physical health, stability of school, teachers' effectiveness, and students' achievement. An educational system's ability to operate and function effectively is correlated with the significance of teachers' well-being (Sarabia & Collantes, 2020).

Teachers in today's era face issues and obstacles such as changing education policies, heavy workloads, unpaid overtime, extra paper works, ancillary responsibilities, work environment, and even students' misbehavior on a day-to-day basis in their workplace has become the reasons why most of them get stressed and tired physically and mentally which make most of them decide to resign from work and seek for greener pasture and satisfaction abroad. Heavy workloads add pressure on teachers' effectiveness fulfilling the major teaching duties. An increase in workloads and responsibilities, and working environment resulted in teachers' burnout and teachers' satisfaction is crucial to their teaching performance.

Thus, the researcher sought to determine the relationship of the work tolerance level of Mathematics teachers in terms of physical demands and psychological demands in relation to their teaching performance as a basis for intervention.

Research Questions

The purpose of the study was to determine the relationship between the work tolerance of Mathematics teachers and their teaching performance. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of Mathematics teachers in terms of:
 - 1.1. sex;
 - 1.2. age;
 - 1.3. socio-economic status;
 - 1.4. highest degree attainment; and
 - 1.5. number of years in service?
2. What is the level of work tolerance of Mathematics teachers when taken as a whole and when taken in terms of:
 - 2.1. physical demands; and

- 2.2. psychological demands?
3. What is the level of Mathematics teachers' teaching performance as a whole and when grouped according to:
 - 3.1. sex;
 - 3.2. age;
 - 3.3. socio-economic status;
 - 3.4. highest degree attainment; and
 - 3.5. number of years in service?
4. Is there a significant difference in the work tolerance of Mathematics teachers when grouped according to the:
 - 4.1. sex;
 - 4.2. age;
 - 4.3. socio-economic status;
 - 4.4. highest degree attainment; and
 - 4.5. number of years in service?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the level of work tolerance of the Mathematics teachers and their teaching performance?
6. Based on the findings of the study, what intervention should be implemented?

Methodology

Research Design

This research determined the relationship of work tolerance in terms of physical and psychological demands on the teaching performance of the Mathematics teachers in all elementary and secondary schools in the District of Isabela - 1 for SY 2023-2024.

The descriptive-correlational design of research was used in this study. According to Bhat (2019), descriptive design is a research design that has a purpose to describe the subject or respondents of the study. Furthermore, it provides an answer to questions that focus on the demographic of the study. The design is used to describe the attributes of the respondents. It also compares groups and validates conditions that exist. The design reveals the overview of the characteristics of the respondents since the purpose of the study is to describe the profile of Mathematics teachers, their work tolerance, and teaching performance.

In addition, a correlational research design is a research method that is used to examine the existing relationship between variables. The design also aims to describe the interrelationships that exist among variables used in the study.

Respondents

The subject and respondents of the study were the Mathematics teachers in the 13 public schools in the District of Isabela – 1 for the school year 2023-2024. All the teachers included in the study were regular-permanent teachers who were handling Mathematics subjects for the current school year.

The sample size of the population was computed using the formula by Slovin. The total population of Mathematics teachers in the District of Isabela 1 for the school year 2023-2024 was one hundred twenty-seven (127) and using the Slovin formula, ninety-six (96) was the obtained sample size.

In determining the number of respondents per school, the researcher used the Stratified Random Sampling Technique

Table 1. Distribution of Respondents per School

School	Population	Sample Size
1	4	3
2	5	4
3	6	5
4	7	5
5	7	5
6	12	9
7	10	8
8	12	9
9	9	7
10	14	11
11	23	17
12	7	5
13	11	8
Total	127	96

After determining the number of sample using the Stratified Random Sampling Technique, the simple random sampling technique in draw lots was employed to identify the respondents from each of the thirteen (13) schools.

Instrument

This study utilized a self-made questionnaire. This is composed of three parts. Part I on the teacher's profile, Part II-A on Physical Demands with 15 statements, and Part II-B on Psychological Demands with 15 statements.

The scores range from 1.00 to 5.00 on the scale indicated below based on the responses that teachers selected such as very high, high, average, low, and very low.

In determining the level of teaching performance of the Mathematics teachers, the Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form was utilized. The scores ranges from 5.00 to 1.00 on the scale indicated based on their performance rating: five for outstanding, four for very satisfactory, three for satisfactory, two for unsatisfactory, and one for poor.

Validity and Reliability of the Research Instrument

In testing the validity of the research instrument, the questionnaire underwent content validity through the expertise of the three jurors, specifically master teachers and coordinators who are experts in the field of Mathematics and Research. The overall mean determined whether the questionnaire was valid or not. Using the rating scale based on the criteria of Carter V. Good and Douglas F. Scates, the research questionnaire obtained a validity index of 3.96.

In testing the reliability, an internal consistency method was used. A reliability test was conducted on forty (40) non-study-participants and the reliability coefficient of 0.968 was determined using Cronbach's alpha. Cronbach's alpha or (coefficient alpha), developed by Lee Cronbach in 1951, measures reliability or internal consistency.

Procedure

To gather data, the researcher sought approval from the Dean of the Graduate School of La Carlota City College and the College President of La Carlota City College. The researcher also sought approval from the Schools Division Superintendent of the Division of Negros Occidental (see Appendix D.2) and the Schools District Supervisor of the District of Isabela – 1 (see Appendix D.7).

After approval was given, the researcher informed and got the consent of the teacher respondents. The researcher then explained the details of the study and after getting the respondents' consent, the researcher distributed the survey forms personally to the respondents who are the Mathematics teachers from all schools in the District of Isabela - 1 of School Year 2023-2024. The researcher then let the teachers respond in the instrument starting from the teacher's profile, work tolerance level, and performance through IPCRF. The survey forms were collected immediately by the researcher to secure the confidentiality of information after giving enough time for the respondents of the study to accomplish it.

Data Analysis

The data obtained in this study was subjected to appropriate descriptive and inferential statistical procedures.

In the analyses and interpretation of data, different statistical tools were used.

To answer statement of the problem no.1 which states, what is the profile of the Mathematics teachers in the District of Isabela - 1 in terms of sex, age, socio-economic status, highest degree attainment, and number of years in service, frequency and percent distribution was used.

To answer the statement of problem no. 2 which states, what the level of work tolerance of Mathematics teachers when taken as a whole and when taken in terms of physical demands and psychological demands, mean was used.

To answer statement of the problem no. 3 which states, what is the level of Mathematics teachers' teaching performance when taken as a whole and when grouped according to sex, age, socio-economic status, highest degree attainment, and number of years in service, mean was used.

To answer statement of the problem no. 4 which states, is there any significant difference in the work tolerance of Mathematics teachers when grouped according to sex, age, highest degree attainment, socio-economic status, and number of years in service, Mann-Whitney U-Test and Kruskal-Wallis H-Test were used.

To answer statement no. 5 which states, is there a significant relationship between the level of work tolerance of the Mathematics teachers and their teaching performance, the Goodman-Kruskal's Gamma (G) or Gamma Coefficient was used.

Results and Discussion

This section deals with the presentation, analyses, and interpretation of the data gathered for this study.

Profile of Mathematics Teachers

The table that follows presents the profile of Mathematics teachers in the District of Isabela 1 in terms of sex, age, socio-economic status, highest educational attainment, and number of years in service.

Table 1. *Frequency and Percent Distribution of Respondents According to Profile*

<i>Profile</i>	<i>Category</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
Sex	Male	16	16.70
	Female	80	83.30
	Total	96	100.00
Age	21-30 years old	24	25.00
	31-40 years old	28	29.17
	41-50 years old	27	28.13
	51 years old and above	17	17.71
	Total	96	100.00
Socio-Economic Status	Rich	7	7.29
	High	0	0
	Upper Middle	7	7.29
	Middle	13	13.54
	Lower Middle	64	66.67
	Low	0	0
	Poor	5	5.21
Total	96	100.00	
Highest Educational Attainment	Bachelor's Degree	60	62.50
	Master's Degree	34	35.42
	Doctorate Degree	2	2.08
	Total	96	100.00
Years in Service	10 years and below	46	47.92
	11-20 years	26	27.08
	21-30 years	15	15.63
	More than 30 years	9	9.38
	Total	96	100.00

Based on the table, it can be observed that in terms of sex, out of 96 Mathematics teachers, 16 are male and 80 or 83.30 percent are female. Thus, there are more females than males with a difference of 64 or 66.6 percent.

In terms of age, 28 or 29.17 percent are between 31-40 years old, followed by 41-50 years old with 27 or 28.13 percent, followed by 21-30 years old with 24 or 25 percent, and the lowest number are the teachers who are 51 years old and above with 17 or 17.71 percent.

In terms of socioeconomic status, most of the teachers belong to lower middle economic status with 64 or 66.67 percent, followed by the middle economic status with 13 or 13.54 percent, and a small percentage of the population belongs to rich and upper middle economic status both with 7 or 7.29 percent, and the lowest number belongs to poor economic status with 5 or 5.21 percent.

When it comes to educational attainment, most of the teachers are bachelor's degree with 60 or 62.50 percent. 34 teachers are master's degree holders, and this comprises 35.42 percent of the total observations. A small percentage of teachers are doctorate holders with 2 or 2.08 percent.

In terms of the number of years in service, most of the teachers are new in the profession, mostly below 10 years in service with 46 or 47.92 percent, followed by 11-20 years in teaching with 26 or 27.08 percent, and then 21-30 years with 15 or 15.63 percent, and a small percentage of teachers that are more than 30 years in service with 9 or 9.38 percent.

Level of Work Tolerance of Mathematics Teachers

The table below reveals the level of work tolerance of Mathematics teachers in the District of Isabela 1 when taken as a whole and when grouped according to physical demands and psychological demands.

Table 2. *Level of Work Tolerance of Mathematics Teachers*

<i>Work Tolerance of Mathematics Teachers</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Physical Demands	96	4.18	High
Psychological Demands	96	4.26	Very High
As a Whole	96	4.218	Very High

The table above shows that the work tolerance of Mathematics teachers in terms of physical demands has a mean of 4.18 and is interpreted as high. In terms of psychological demands, the work tolerance of Mathematics teachers has a mean of 4.26 and is interpreted as very high. As a whole, the work tolerance of Mathematics teachers has a mean of 4.218 and is interpreted as very high.

The results suggest that Mathematics teachers are more tolerant in their work in terms of psychological demands. This means that

teachers can all the time do their work effectively and efficiently without any adverse effects on their psychological well-being. However, though their work tolerance in terms of physical demands is high, teachers must also consider improvement in their work that requires physical demands.

The result is supported by the study of Dhanpat, de Braine & Geldenhuys (2019) and Ngoc, Hoang & Hung (2020). Demands experienced comprise hefty workloads, time and resource restrictions, extended working hours, ensuring that support is provided, and staying abreast of technological developments. The physically drained teachers according to that study perceived their roles as more demanding than their occupations and saw themselves as less competent. Physical demands may be a factor in their poor performance, prolonged sick leave, or teacher attrition. According to research, the goal of teacher education is to prepare and develop teachers, and this process does not end when a teacher completes their degree. When claiming incapacity to work, the general public frequently uses physical complaints – such as back pain, chest pain, shortness of breath, heart palpitations, issues with sleep or appetite, and fatigue – instead of psychological complaints (Donaghy, 2018). According to Gul and Alimbejov (2020), Gunduz (2019), and Muhammed (2019), some studies have revealed that the work tolerance levels of teachers are at a partially high level, however, some are at a low level according to Cargiga (2020).

Level of Teaching Performance Of Mathematics Teachers According to Profile

The table on the next page shows the level of Mathematics teachers' teaching performance in terms of sex, age, socio-economic status, highest educational attainment, and years in service.

Table 3. *Level of Teaching Performance of Mathematics Teachers According to Profile*

<i>Profile</i>	<i>Category</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Sex	Male	16	4.88	Outstanding
	Female	80	4.69	Outstanding
	Total	96	4.72	Outstanding
Age	21-30 years old	24	4.67	Outstanding
	31-40 years old	28	4.82	Outstanding
	41-50 years old	27	4.78	Outstanding
	51 years old and above	17	4.53	Outstanding
	Total	96	4.72	Outstanding
Socio-Economic Status	Rich	7	5.00	Outstanding
	High	0	0.00	
	Upper Middle	7	4.57	Outstanding
	Middle	13	4.62	Outstanding
	Lower Middle	64	4.73	Outstanding
	Low	0	0.00	
	Poor	5	4.60	Outstanding
Total	96	4.72	Outstanding	
Highest Educational Attainment	Bachelor's Degree	60	4.72	Outstanding
	Master's Degree	34	4.74	Outstanding
	Doctorate Degree	2	4.50	Outstanding
	Total	96	4.72	Outstanding
Years in Service	10 years and below	46	4.72	Outstanding
	11-20 years	26	4.81	Outstanding
	21-30 years	15	4.8	Outstanding
	More than 30 years	9	4.33	Very Satisfactory
	Total	96	4.72	Outstanding

Based on the table above, it can be observed that in terms of sex, both male and female teachers have the same level of teaching performance with means of 4.88 and 4.69 respectively, and can be interpreted as outstanding. This means that both sex have teaching performance that exceeds extraordinary levels of achievement and commitment according to the required criteria. However, the obtained mean for male teachers exceeds the obtained mean for female teachers with a little difference of 0.19.

This is supported by the statement that heterogeneous preferences and beliefs have major implications in the field of work. Heterogeneity across genders is especially relevant – each group includes half of the population, and there are systematic differences in the preferences of men and women, which in turn have large effects (Bertnard et al., 2018).

In terms of age, it can be observed that teachers aged 31-40 years old have the highest mean of 4.82 followed by those aged 41-50 years old with a mean of 4.78, and then those aged 21-30 years old with a mean 4.67, and then followed by 51 years old and above which has the lowest mean of 4.53, and each can be interpreted as outstanding.

The result is in conformity with the study of Miglioretti et al. (2018) and Gragnano et al. (2019) which said that age is one of the factors

that affects work performance since as we grow older, we become more prone to sleep problems and other health complications. Worker's health and job productivity and performance are two main issues that need to be addressed as they age, and they are kept together in the sustainability perspective.

Mathematics teachers' performance in terms of age in all categories can be interpreted as outstanding. This means that the teaching performance of mathematics teachers exceeds an extraordinary level of achievement and commitment according to the required criteria.

In terms of socio-economic status, it can be observed that teachers that belong to rich economic status have the highest mean of 5.00, followed by teachers in the lower middle category with a mean of 4.73, followed by teachers in the middle category with a mean of 4.62, the teachers in the poor category with a mean of 4.60, and lastly followed by teachers in the upper middle category with the lowest mean of 4.57. The teaching performance of mathematics teachers in all these categories is each interpreted as outstanding.

This means that regardless of socio-economic status, teachers can perform their work that exceeds extraordinary levels of achievement and commitment according to the required criteria.

In terms of highest educational attainment, it can be observed on the table that teachers with master's degrees have the highest level of teaching performance with a mean of 4.74, followed by teachers who are bachelor's degree holders with a mean of 4.72 and a little difference of 0.02. It can also be observed in the table that teachers with doctorate degrees have the lowest level of teaching performance among the three categories with a mean of 4.50. Each mean in all categories can be interpreted as outstanding. This means that teachers can work that exceeds extraordinary levels of achievement and commitment according to prescribed standards and criteria.

In terms of number of years in service, it can be observed on the table that teachers with 11-20 years of experience in teaching have the highest mean of 4.81, and teachers with 21-30 years of teaching with a mean of 4.81, and with a little difference of 0.01. Both means of these categories are interpreted as outstanding. Meanwhile, those teachers with 10 years and below experience in teaching have a mean of 4.72 and is interpreted as outstanding, followed by teachers with more than 30 years of teaching experience with the lowest mean of 4.33 and is interpreted as very satisfactory.

In line with Lakshmita et al. (2022), the duration of an employee's service to a company and the degree of his productivity contribute to his ability to do the job well. He also said that the demand for work, job resources, and personality are factors that influence the working period. Moreover, the length of period a person works affects his skills and speed in doing his job.

When it comes to length of service, Suryadi, Agustin, & Sukarno (2018) said that performance and behaviors related to the workplace are significantly impacted by organizational and job tenure. People develop professionally through their occupations, which help them gain knowledge, experience, and skills that increase their productivity at work.

As a whole, the teaching performance of Mathematics teachers has a mean of 4.72 and is interpreted as outstanding. The result suggests that the teaching performance of Mathematics teachers demonstrates an exceptional degree of accomplishment and dedication in terms of time, quality, technical expertise, inventiveness, and initiative, though there is still room for improvement. However, the result implies that there is still a need to strengthen the performance of teachers, especially those with 30 and above years of teaching experience since this is the only category that has the lowest mean that can be interpreted as very satisfactory compared to other categories which can be interpreted as outstanding.

Difference in the Level of Work Tolerance of Mathematics Teachers When Grouped According to Sex

The table on the next page reveals the difference in the level of work tolerance of Mathematics teachers when grouped according to sex.

Table 4.1. *Difference in the Level of Work Tolerance of Mathematics Teachers When Grouped According to Sex*

<i>Sex</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>Mean Rank</i>
Male	16	53.16
Female	80	47.57
Total	96	

Computed Value(U) = 565.50

P-Value = 0.464

Decision = Accept Ho

Interpretation = Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

Based on Table 4.1, the 80 female Mathematics teachers have and a mean rank of 47.57. Whereas the 16 male Mathematics teachers have a mean rank of 53.16.

Using the Mann-Whitney Test at a 0.05 significance level, the U-computed value of 565.50 was obtained and a p-value of 0.464 is greater than the significance level. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that there is no significant difference in the work tolerance of Mathematics teachers when grouped according to sex.

This implies that sex does not make a difference in the level of work tolerance of Mathematics teachers. Regardless that teachers are male or female, this does not guarantee one has a higher level of work tolerance than the other.

The result is in contrast with Schmude & Jackisch (2019) who said that it is also critical to acknowledge that teaching is a gendered profession, with a greater proportion of women than males working in the field.

Moreover, supporting teacher wellbeing is understudied, especially in light of gender (Bourgeault et al., 2021). Attitudes toward work may differ between men and women because societal perceptions of what constitutes acceptable and unacceptable employment are shaped by commonly held gender stereotypes.

Difference in the Level of Work Tolerance of Mathematics Teachers When Grouped According to Age

The table that follows reveals the difference in the level of work tolerance of Mathematics teachers when grouped according to age.

Table 4.2. *Difference in the Level of Work Tolerance of Mathematics Teachers When Grouped According to Age*

Age	f	Mean Rank
21-30 years old	24	50.44
31-40 years old	28	46.73
41-50 years old	27	50.81
51 years old and above	17	45.00
Total	96	

Computed Value(H) = 0.86

P-Value = 0.835

Decision = Accept Ho

Interpretation = Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

Based on Table 4.2, in terms of age, Mathematics teachers aged 41-50 years old with a frequency of 27 have the highest mean rank of 50.81 while teachers aged 51 years old and above have the lowest mean rank of 45.00.

Using the Kruskal Wallis Test at a 0.05 level of significance, the H-computed value of 0.86 was obtained and a p-value of 0.835 is greater than the significance level. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that there is no significant difference in the work tolerance of Mathematics teachers when grouped according to age. This implies that age does not make a difference in the level of work tolerance of Mathematics teachers. Regardless that teachers are young or old at age, whether they are in their 20s or 50s, this does not guarantee one has a higher level of work tolerance over the other.

However, the result is contrary to the study of Miglioretti et al., 2018 and Gragnano et al., 2019 which said that age is one of the factors that affect work performance since as we grow older, we become more prone to sleep problems and other health complications. Worker's health and job productivity and performance are two main issues that need to be addressed as they age, and they are kept together in the sustainability perspective.

Furthermore, numerous studies have suggested that a younger age is associated with a better tolerance at work, with indications suggesting the critical age for decreasing tolerance to work is between 40 and 50 years old. However, research on the association between work tolerance and age has yielded contradictory results where work tolerance may increase with age. Age-related differences in work tolerance may be biologically plausible, despite the lack of good evidence in this area.

Difference in the Level of Work Tolerance of Mathematics Teachers When Grouped According to Socio-Economic Status

The table on the next page reveals the difference in the level of work tolerance of Mathematics teachers when grouped according to socio-economic status.

Table 4.3. *Difference in the Level of Work Tolerance of Mathematics Teachers When Grouped According to Socio-economic Status*

Socio-Economic Status	f	Mean Rank
Rich	7	44.36
High	0	0.00
Upper Middle	7	35.00
Middle	13	54.46
Lower Middle	64	50.33
Low	0	0.00
Poor	5	34.30
Total	96	

Computed Value(H) = 4.98

P-Value = 0.289

Decision = Accept Ho

Interpretation = Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

It can be observed in Table 4.3 that most of the Mathematics teachers belong to the lower middle category of socio-economic status with a frequency of 64 out of 96 and a mean rank of 50.33. It can also be observed that 5 teachers belong to the poor category with a mean rank of 34.40 which is also the lowest among the mean ranks. This means that most of the teachers are not economically stable considering the ratio of their monthly pay to their expenses.

Using the Kruskal Wallis Test at a 0.05 level of significance, the H-computed value of 4.98 was obtained and a p-value of 0.289 is greater than the level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that there is no significant difference in the work tolerance of Mathematics teachers when grouped according to socio-economic status. This implies that socio-economic status does not make a difference in the level of work tolerance of Mathematics teachers. Regardless of how much teachers earn in a month, whether they are rich or poor, belonging to upper middle or lower middle, financially stable, or not, this does not guarantee one has a higher level of work tolerance over the other.

However, the result is in contrast with the claim of Am J Ind Med (2020) which is a low socioeconomic status is known to be associated with more frequent work problems. People of the lowest socioeconomic status are more likely to have work problems than those of high socioeconomic status. The idea that stress reactions are the outcome of an imbalance between supply and demand provides a broad explanation for this, as people with lower socioeconomic positions are more likely to be exposed to situations that pose a threat to their health and life, but they also have fewer resources available to them to deal with these difficulties. People living in underprivileged environments, for instance, maybe more vulnerable to dangers, disputes, and uncertainties, to which there are frequently insufficient resources to adequately respond.

Difference in the Level of Work Tolerance of Mathematics Teachers When Grouped According to Educational Attainment

The table on the next page reveals the difference in the level of work tolerance of Mathematics teachers when grouped according to educational attainment.

Table 4.4. *Difference in the Level of Work Tolerance of Mathematics Teachers When Grouped According to Educational Attainment*

<i>Highest Educational Attainment</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>Mean Rank</i>
Bachelor's Degree	60	54.59
Master's Degree	34	37.81
Doctorate Degree	2	47.50
Total	96	

Computed Value(H) = 9.89
P-Value = 0.007
Decision = Reject Ho
Interpretation = Significant at 0.05 level of significance

Based on Table 4.4, out of 96 Mathematics teachers, 60 have finished their bachelor's degree with the mean rank of 54.49. It can be observed also that only two teachers have doctorate degree with the mean mean rank of 47.50.

Using the Kruskal Wallis Test at a 0.05 level of significance, the H-computed value of 9.89 was obtained and a p-value of 0.007 is less than the significance level of 0.05, thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that there is a significant difference in the work tolerance of Mathematics teachers when grouped according to educational attainment. This implies that education plays a vital role in the work tolerance of teachers. It also implies that education guarantees that one teacher has a higher level of work tolerance than the other. Teachers who are filled with knowledge and skills are more tolerant in their work when compared to teachers that do not have any of those. The success of educational organizations and teacher performance have a strong correlation because of teacher education and qualifications.

The result is supported by a study that said that teachers who are tolerant to stress are thought to result from their education as well as a few other factors according to Holley et. al. (2019), and Pitogo and Ecle (2021). The teaching profession requires multidimensional individuals who possess knowledge and skills in social, cultural, science, and technology.

High levels of education in teachers result in more effective work and training, better student-teacher interaction, a greater willingness to implement contemporary teaching strategies, the use of a variety of teaching aids and methods, support for students' learning even in challenging circumstances, a high level of motivation, effort, and patience, an impact on student's success, and research to improve the quality of instruction and training provided in the classroom (Skaalvik and Skaalvik, 2019).

Furthermore, the teachers' professional knowledge and skills were cited as a factor contributing to teacher positive outlook in work in four studies (Dasan & Nawi, 2020; Altunova & Kalman, 2020; Muhidin et al., 2019; Atmotiyoso & Huda, 2018).

Difference in the Level of Work Tolerance of Mathematics Teachers When Grouped According to Number of Years in Service

The table below reveals the difference in the level of work tolerance of Mathematics teachers when grouped according to the number of years in service.

Based on Table 4.5, the 46 teachers with 10 and below years in service have a mean rank of 50.97. In contrast, for teachers with more than 30 years in service, there are 9 observations with a mean rank of 37.78. For teachers with 11-20 and 21-30 years in service with a frequency of 26 have a mean rank of 47.54, and 15 observations with a mean rank of 49.03, respectively.

Using the Kruskal Wallis Test at a 0.05 level of significance, the H-computed value of 2.17 was obtained and a p-value of 0.537 which is greater than the significance level, thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that there is no significant difference in the work

tolerance of Mathematics teachers when grouped according to the number of years of teaching. This implies that whether a teacher is newly hired or a retiree, this does not affect its level of work tolerance. Regardless of how long a teacher has been in the teaching profession, this does not guarantee that he has a higher level of work tolerance the others.

Table 4.5. *Difference in the Level of Work Tolerance of Mathematics Teachers When Grouped According to Number of Years in Service*

<i>Years in Service</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>Mean</i>
10 years and below	46	50.97
11-20 years	26	47.54
21-30 years	15	49.03
More than 30 years	9	37.78
Total	96	

Computed Value(H) = 2.17
P-Value = 0.537
Decision = Accept Ho
Interpretation = Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

The results imply that the years in service do not impact his work tolerance. As the years added, commitment level increases but not motivational and work tolerance level. Surprisingly, number of years in work doesn't influence employee behavior and tolerance at work as both newly employed as well as old veterans (Becker S., 2018).

The result is congruent with the statemnet of Ukas (2019) that the amount of time a teacher has contributed to an institution and the level to which his ability to function properly does not influence his tolerance at work. He asserts that a person's working duration has no significant impact on their productivity and skill level.

However, regarding years in service, Atatsi (2019) stated that organizational structure and length of service have a significant impact on behaviors and output connected to the workplace. People develop professionally through their vocations, which help them gain information, experience, and abilities that increase their productivity at work.

Relationship Between the Levels Of Work Tolerance of The Mathematics Teachers And Their Teaching Performance

The table below reveals the relationship between the level of work tolerance of Mathematics teachers in the District of Isabela 1 to their teaching performance.

Table 5. *Relationship Between the Level of Work Tolerance of Mathematics Teachers and their Teaching Performance*

<i>Level of Work Tolerance of Mathematics Teachers</i>	<i>Level of Teaching Performance</i>					<i>Total</i>
	<i>Outstanding</i>	<i>Very Satisfactory</i>	<i>Satisfactory</i>	<i>Unsatisfactory</i>	<i>Poor</i>	
Very High	38	11	1	0	0	50
High	31	7	0	0	0	38
Average	3	3	1	0	0	7
Low	0	0	0	0	0	0
Very Low	0	0	1	0	0	1
Total	72	21	3	0	0	96

Computed Value(H) = -0.20
P-Value = 0.378
Decision = Accept Ho
Interpretation = Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

The table reveals that most of the Mathematics teachers in the district of Isabela 1 obtained an outstanding level of teaching performance based on their IPCRF for the current school year with a frequency of 72 out of 96 teachers in total. The work of these educators demonstrates an exceptional degree of accomplishment and dedication in terms of timeliness, technical proficiency, inventiveness, and initiative. Out of 96 Mathematics teachers, 38 obtained a rating of outstanding with a very high level of work tolerance. Eleven Mathematics teachers got very satisfactory rating with very high level of work tolerance, and only one got satisfactory rating with a very high level of work tolerance. Meanwhile, 31 of them have an outstanding and 7 have very satisfactory rating with high level of work tolerance, respectively.

Also, 21 Mathematics teachers got a very satisfactory rating in their IPCRF with 11 of them whose level of work tolerance is very high, 7 and 3 are of high and average level, respectively.

On the other hand, out of these 96 Mathematics teachers, there are 3 teachers whose teaching performance rating is of satisfactory level only. This means that these teachers' performance met expectations in terms of quality of work, efficiency, and timeliness. The most critical annual goals were met. Out of these 3 teachers, 1 has a very high level of work tolerance, 1 with an average, and 1 also with a very low level of work tolerance.

Based also on the table presented above, there are a total of 50 Mathematics teachers whose level of work tolerance is very high, 38 of them have a high level, 7 have an average level, and 1 has a very low level of work tolerance.

Using the Goodman-Kruskal's Gamma (G) or Gamma Coefficient at a 0.05 level of significance, the G-computed value of -0.20 was obtained, and a p-value of 0.378 is greater than the significance level. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that there is no significant relationship between the work tolerance of Mathematics teachers and their teaching performance. This implies that the work tolerance level of Mathematics teachers has nothing to do with the rating they obtained in their IPCRF. Whether the teacher performs extraordinarily, this does not guarantee one has a higher level of work tolerance over the other.

The result is supported by Siman, Sulaiman & Effendi, 2019 who said, the workability of a teacher is seen from the level of achievement and the completion of the tasks that are his responsibility by the conditions set in a field of work.

Teaching performance, according to Suryadi, Agustin, and Sukarno (2018), is the outcome of a teacher's work or activities in carrying out his responsibilities in managing the learning activities in the quantity and quality within an organization (school) to meet the established standards and goals.

The outcome of work that can be accomplished by an individual or group of individuals within an organization, in compliance with each person's authority and responsibilities, in an attempt to legally accomplish the goals of the organization in question, does not contravene legal requirements or moral or ethical standards (Gewasari, Manullang & Sibuea, 2018).

Teachers are expected to perform well in light of the changes aimed at improving the educational system. These include handling a large volume of paperwork, managing the behavior of a changing student body, attending multiple seminars, reporting, and receiving training. These demands can lead to psychological problems like stress, work dissatisfaction, disengagement, and in the worst cases, suicide, depression, and anxiety. Furthermore, prior research demonstrates that there has been little investigation into the relationship between work-related stress and teacher performance, as evidenced by the works of Alson and Tiqui (n.d.), Ansley, Meyers, McPhee, and Varjas (2018), and Asthana and Owen (2018).

Conclusions

Based on the foregoing findings of this research study, the conclusions that were arrived at are as follows:

There are more female than male Mathematics teachers; most of the teachers are 41-50 years old, while very few teachers are 51 years old and above; more than half of the total number of Mathematics teachers belong to lower middle economic status with monthly gross income of ₱18,200 – ₱36,400 based on Philippine Institute for Development Studies (PIDS 2023); 62.5 percent of teachers are bachelor's degree holder while 2.08 percent are doctorate holder; and most of the Mathematics teachers are new in the teaching profession with a teaching experience of 10 years and below.

Mathematics teachers are more tolerant in their work in terms of psychological demands.

The teaching performance of Mathematics teachers in the District of Isabela 1 when grouped according to sex, age, socio-economic status and educational attainment is outstanding. When grouped according to the number of years in service, their teaching performance is outstanding, with 30 years and above category which yields the rating of very satisfactory. As a whole, the teaching performance of Mathematics teachers in the District of Isabela 1 is outstanding.

The work tolerance level of Mathematics teachers does not vary in terms of sex, age, socio-economic status, and number of years in the teaching profession. However, the work tolerance level of Mathematics teachers varies when grouped according to educational attainment.

The work tolerance level of Mathematics teachers does not affect their teaching performance.

Concerning the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are offered:

Schools can focus on building a habit of daily physical exercise for their teachers. Teachers may take a break occasionally. Rest when needed, if possible, to help maintain productivity and effectiveness as well as personal well-being.

Teachers can maintain an outstanding level of teaching performance, especially teachers with 30 years and above of teaching experience. It is important to annually evaluate one's self-strengths and weaknesses as a teacher. Be teachable and open-minded with the current trends in education. Schools can organize workshops and seminars on modern approaches and strategies in teaching.

Teachers may engage in professional development by obtaining a higher education degree. Aside from earning a higher degree, teachers can continue learning and try also to engage in seminars, and workshops, and learn new ways and experiences relating to the field of teaching.

The school together with the District of Isabela 1 can plan out and craft more improved approaches and strategies for teachers to release stress and fatigue, and if possible, lessen the ancillary works and loads of teachers, to maintain and improve further their physical and psychological well-being. This is to ensure that teachers feel valued and cared for.

Teachers may equip themselves with the necessary capabilities and skills in both physical and psychological aspects, that would enable them to properly utilize their capacity to the different working demands they are expected to exert their effort to.

The quality of teaching imparted to students and the level of work tolerance and attitude a teacher has must come together in hand to ensure that learners in today's challenging times are filled with the quality and complete education the Department of Education is pursuing in its mission and vision.

For future researchers, it is recommended to conduct further studies on work tolerance, attitude, and performance of teachers including other variables and skills not mentioned in the current study.

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